

Horizon Europe

Career Development Plan

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Call: HORIZON-MSCA-2022-PF-01

(MSCA Postdoctoral Fellowships 2022)

Topic: HORIZON-MSCA-2022-PF-01-01

Type of Action: HORIZON-TMA-MSCA-PF-EF. (HORIZON TMA MSCA Postdoctoral Fellowships - European Fellowships)

Proposal number: 101103095

Proposal acronym: Trans Modernismo

Full title: Birth of the Marimacho: Modernismo's Trans* Cultural Productions in Latin America

Researcher: Dr. Carlos Gustavo Halaburda

Supervisor: Prof. Dr. Peter Schulze.

Type of Model Grant Agreement: HORIZON Unit Grant

Department: Universitat zu Koln. Department of Romance Studies. Germany

Starting Date: 1/09/2023

Duration (in months): 24

Scientific Area: SOC - Social Sciences and Humanities (SOC); gender history; cultural studies; cultural diversity; literary theory and comparative literature; literary styles; women and gender studies; libraries and archives.

CAREER DEVELOPMENT PLAN
YEAR 1

1. BRIEF OVERVIEW OF RESEARCH PROJECT AND MAJOR ACCOMPLISHMENTS EXPECTED (HALF PAGE SHOULD BE SUFFICIENT)

Birth of the Marimacho: Modernismo's Trans Cultural Productions in Latin America* analyzes the emergence of a new gender expression in early-twentieth-century Latin American literature, medical science, and visual culture: the «marimacho». In the Hispanic tradition, *marimacho* is the umbrella notion that may refer to a sexist slur as much as a modern form of non-binary gender, a transmasculine identification, or a lesbian identity. This project examines the aesthetic construction of this hybrid, counter-cultural, and gender-dissident figure in an extensive cultural repertoire that includes novels, plays, films, leaflets, medical studies, prison and mental hospital records, poems, newspaper, and tabloid articles. The research draws upon multiple theoretical schools and philosophical resources from gender and sexuality studies, especially queer theory. Queer scholarship addresses not only the political self-representation of LGBTQ bodies. Queer studies also examine major problems in minority discourse: the medical stigmas around homosexuality and transness, the non-normative/non-reproductive uses of erotic pleasures, and the broad implications of 'gender dysphoria' for orthodox notions of citizenship. In this sense, I examine the specificity of practices carried out by a rich plethora of fin-de-siècle Latin American female and trans*masculine subcultures as well as some figures of male queerness: uranistas and maricas (homosexuals) soldaderas (women soldiers), llaneras (rural women), cuchilleras (knife fighters), arrabaleras (tango singers), bollerías (tomboys), safistas and invertidas (lesbian & trans* masculine identities), vampiras (criollo vernacular for hysterics), and other gender-dissident figures of the turn of the century. My analysis of the chosen corpus will demonstrate how queer men, lesbians and trans*men contested misogynist and sexual slurs by showing how gender and sexual orientation, far from being natural, are both constructed through performance and the adoption of diverse prosthetic artifacts, from hair and clothing to makeup and other cosmetics. I seek to increase the understanding of the region's politics of gender and sexuality during the modernizing era (1880s-1930s), that is, before the solidification of LGBTQ activism, pride literature, and minority social movements of the global 1960s. In response to the new gender dynamics led by fin-de-siècle cosmopolitan networks of first-wave feminism and secret homosexual fraternities, the keepers of gender normativity created the *marimacho* as a monstrous version of conventional masculinity. The main objective of this research is to investigate why a broad range of cultural materials named queer men and women, non-binary individuals, and trans* men as *marimachos*, as gender hackers that put at stake the Latin American futures of heteronormativity, reproduction, and family life.

This project is committed to a transformative scholarly framework that validates the cultural memory of stigmatized Latin American gender and sexual minorities. It seeks to recognize and give visibility to the epistemic, cultural, and institutional violence historically endured by the LGBTQ community. This project addresses the late nineteenth- and early twentieth-century legacies of homophobia, transphobia, and misogyny recorded in the literary and scientific archives of the region, with a global perspective. In my combination of literary criticism, historical work, archival research, and the critique of past sexual and medical taxonomies, I read against the grain of the original violence that represented LGBTQ peoples as abject subjects unworthy of full citizenship in the cultural production of the period 1880-1930. My research will be an opportunity to challenge official narratives about gender and sexual minorities. A principal goal of my research is to expand the cultural history of queer Latino collectives. The attention to queer cultural memory will acknowledge the historical stigmatization of LGBTQ peoples persecuted by state power and endured confinement in prisons and mental hospitals in the early twentieth century.

Ultimately, this is a research project that seeks historical restitution for past Latin American LGBTQ groups.

My project's target audience includes: (1) academic institutions; (2) public libraries; (3) NGOs such as the Cologne Rainbow City Network; (4) the LGBTQ+ community, and (5) the general public.

• **Expected accomplishments:**

- **Academic publications:** 1) A monograph in an open access university press, possibly in Argentina (Universidad Nacional de La Plata); 2) a special issue in an open access journal; 3) three singled-authored articles to be submitted to open access journals in Europe and the Americas. Details below.
- **Dissemination and visibility:** 1) Public presentations and campus seminars; 2) Scientific conferences; 3) Website; 4) Engagement with LGBTQ cultural initiatives, especially in Germany; 5) General media; 6) Policy community impact.
- **Professionalization:** 1) Grants; 2) Teaching; 3) Supervision; 4) Networking.

The described expected achievements will be detailed and developed in the following pages, differentiating the results achieved so far from the expected ones.

LONG-TERM CAREER OBJECTIVES (Five Years)

Quality and pertinence of the project's research and innovation objectives. Given the continuous stigma faced by the LGBTQ Global South community, research and social engagement to promote equality, human rights, and inclusive education is the primary goal of my academic agenda. I am an active early-career scholar who collaborated with pedagogical initiatives for international public and academic institutions with the mission to educate against homophobia, racism, and antisemitism. With my expertise in articulating academic work with the public sector, I am certain that the research findings resulted from my postdoctoral work in Germany funded by the MSCA will contribute to the scholarship on the epistemic and institutional violence against LGBTQ and racialized peoples. Taking Latin America as a case study, my scientific advances achieved during my postdoctoral residence will create new knowledge about the power relations between doctors, law makers, intellectuals, and artists with gender and sexual minorities. Academics, activists, and NGO leaders will benefit from this work, whose goal is to promote LGBTQ culture, visibility, and memory.

Thanks to the support of the European Commission, I am confident that I will be able to become an internationally recognized scholar in gender and sexuality studies. In the next five years, I want to acquire new methodological approaches that will enable me to grow in my expertise on queer Latin American Studies and disseminate my results in academic and non-academic spaces of high prestige in Europe and the Americas. The goals of my research scheme include several ambitious axes, from research and writing to teaching and dissemination actions. If the completion of these packages is compromised, I will reassess with my advisor my future working schedule. I have discussed a plan with my supervisor Prof. Dr. Schulze. The long-term plans include:

Academic publication:

(1) A monograph to be submitted possibly to the National University of La Plata Press. Originally, in my proposal, I proposed the University of Toronto Press. But since this press is not open access, I would consider the prestigious open access press Universidad Nacional de La Plata, one of the most important

and recognized open repositories in the world: <https://www.editorial.unlp.edu.ar/genero>. This monograph is a long-term project that will extend the period of the tenure of my MSCA fellowship.

(2) A special issue co-edited with a collaborator from The University of Cologne and other European universities potentially titled *Re-Monstering Gender: Aesthetics of Transitioning in Contemporary Latin American Art and Literature*. This dossier proposal will be submitted possibly to the Brazilian open access journal *Sexualidad, Salud & Sociedad: Revista Latinoamericana*, published by the Universidade do Estado do Rio de Janeiro. But other journals are being considered such as *Gender Studies: The Journal of West University, Timisoara, Interdisciplinary Centre for Gender Studies* (Poland); (3) Three singled-authored articles to be submitted to the open access journals possibly a) *Iberoamericana* (Ibero-Amerikanisches Institut, Germany), b) *Anclajes* (Universidad de La Pampa, Argentina) and c) *Genre, Sexualité & Société* (Centre national de la recherche scientifique, France). These articles will analyze the following topics: (a) the medicalized depiction of male queerness, trans*masculine expression and transvestism in literature; (b) the types of transgender affirmation that novelists, doctors, and playwrights condemned as ‘sexual inversion’ and crimes ‘against morality’; and (c) the role of disciplines such as endocrinology, psychiatry, legal medicine, and criminology in the making of the *marimacho*, a ‘monster gender’, a somatic construction that helped to solidify the *cishetero* scientific notion of ‘gender dysphoria.’

Scientific conferences:

I will attend:

- The Latin American Studies Association Congress (June 2024/May 2025)
- Society for Latin American Studies (SLAS) Annual Conference 2025 (UK), among possible others.

Website:

To promote the circulation of LGBTQ-related literary and artistic traditions, aesthetic schools, and queer social movements in Latin America, I will create the *Queer Americas Ancestry Digital Humanities Project*. The website will feature blog entries and it will include a repository of copyright-free images, clinical testimonies, interviews, tabloid newspapers, and other archival work gathered through my years of research. This initiative will communicate cultural content related to the rich history of queer people and will start to take place in the last stages of my project, possibly with the help of research assistants.

Public presentations and campus seminars:

As the stages of my investigation unfold, I will deliver and discuss my findings with colleagues of the host department and affiliated institutes at the University of Cologne. I will also plan, propose, and convene a scholarly gathering for interdisciplinary dialogue among German and English researchers and graduate students. This forum will address different issues of Trans* Studies in the Americas in a conference for the year 2025 that I will propose to the University of Cologne’ Global South Studies Center potentially titled, *Gender Hackers: Bio-Art and the Trans*Subversion of Cis-heteronormativity*.

Engagement with LGBTQ cultural initiatives in Germany:

I will contact the Schwules Museum (Gay Museum) in Berlin and the Schwules Centrum in Cologne and propose an exhibition on Fin-De-Siècle Queer Latin America. I will also contact centers in Canada such as The Bonham Centre for Sexual Diversity Studies. In Argentina, I will contact the Cultural Center Casa Brandon. This show would take place in the years 2025 or 2026 and will feature photographs, literature, pamphlets, medical studies, and letters, among other objects related to different issues of queer life, such as places of cruising, sex work, prison and mental hospital life, and the political reception of the Oscar Wild trials in Latin America, a foundational moment of homosexual visibility in the Americas.

Other training skills

During my residence at the University of Cologne, I will strengthen my training by partaking in specific actions. The plan is as follows:

1. Audit a course offered by the Department of Romance Studies to gain pedagogical experience and develop new teaching skills. **(Achieved)**
2. Teach an advanced seminar. **(Achieved)**
3. Participate in other departmental activities to gain experience in service and administration.
4. Prof. Dr. Schulze is my primary contact, providing advice on several aspects: 1) Publication schedule; 2) conference and seminar expositions; 3) pedagogical training portfolio, and 4) funding capture and the job market.
5. Present preliminary research results in departmental seminars. **(Achieved)**
6. Participate in training procedures, seminars, and workshops offered by the University of Cologne. For example, the Open Science (Open Access and Open Data) Webinar (NCP ERC Webinar on Open Science in ERC projects (19.03.2024, 13:00-14:30).
7. Privilege independent work.
8. The host department with the Portuguese-Brazilian Institute and the affiliated academic institutions will be involved actors in the development and fulfillment of my future plans.
9. I will be assisted by the University of Cologne Personnel Development Dialogues (PDD) for Researchers, the Global South Studies Center, the Erich Auerbach Institute for Advanced Studies, the Postdoc Career Program, and the Albertus Magnus Center for professionalization. In what follows, I outline what I achieved so far during the implementation of the initiative.

SHORT-TERM OBJECTIVES

Research Results

- Anticipated publications:

Articles:

1. **The Machona Affair: Queering Masculinity in Buenos Aires 1920s Print Culture.** Article to be submitted to the journal *Iberoamericana* (Berlin). <https://journals.iai.spk-berlin.de/index.php/iberoamericana>. **Fall 2024.** Subject to schedule revision.

Abstract. *La Garçonne* (1922) by the French writer Victor Margueritte provoked international scandal during the Interwar period (1918-1939) as the novel portrayed a queer romance between two women of

the Parisian bourgeoisie. The turn-of-the-century Naturalist novel à la Émile Zola associated female homosexuality with plebeian groups and sex work. Erotic relationships between high-society women had rarely been a novelistic topic in the fin de siècle, for which Margueritte endured repudiation from French literary circles. In the Southern Cone, with the Spanish translation and extraordinary success of *La Garçonne* [La machona], queer forms of masculine embodiment and same-sex desire became thematic trends in numerous literary, musical, and visual works. This presentation will discuss how tango songs, plays, novels, illustrations, and magazine articles addressed the garçonne scandal, generating a crucial debate about the stability and instability of conventional gender and sexual protocols in 1920s Buenos Aires. By engaging with a series of texts by Horacio Quiroga, Abraham Valdelomar, Isaac Morales, Luis Cané, and Osvaldo Sosa Cordero, Halaburda explores how la machona became a counter-cultural identity that disputed gender binarism and early-twentieth-century notions of womanhood, decorum, femininity, and masculinity, turning into an essential chapter in South American LGBTIQ history.

- 2. A Cosmopolitan Uranism: Queer Networks of Scandal in the Global Nineteenth Century. To be submitted to the journal *Genre, Sexualité, & Société* (Winter 2025). <https://journals.openedition.org/gss/>. Subject to schedule revision.**

Abstract. This article examines the role of disgust in the nineteenth century medico-legal construction of homosexuality as a cosmopolitan scandalous identity able to undermine national imaginaries based on patriotism, marriage and reproduction, decorum, and respectability. I argue that medical expressions of disgust at the presence of queer populations in the public space was at the core of the historical, social, and scientific analysis of the homosexual scandal in the global nineteenth century. Medico-legal research, literature, the visual arts, and judicial reports reveal in the archives of global queer histories numerous homosexual scandals that provoked a global call for a “hunt” against gender and sexual transgressions in the name of national security. Via the lens of a European-Latin American exchange circuit, I show how global networks of nineteenth century sexology illustrate the transmission, translation, and adaption of scientific and literary discourses concerning homosexual scandals. I engage with a series of excerpts of forensic sexology and journalistic chronicles of the queer underworlds in Berlin, Paris, Buenos Aires, and Rio de Janeiro. By affording due significance to scandal as a technology of queer subjectivation, I unveil a «queer micropolitics» marked by a deliberate detachment from imperial, national, and hetero-normative imaginaries.

- 3. A Crip Sentimentality: Tramps, Deviants, and the Sign of Queerness and Disability. To be submitted to the journal *Anclajes*. <https://cerac.unlpam.edu.ar/index.php/anclajes> (Spring 2025). Subject of schedule revision.**

Abstract. This chapter explores how the medical criteria of Argentine positivist science and literary naturalism promoted an ableist view towards the so-called “transient” body. The tramps (*los atorrantes*) and their multiple vernacular affiliations (*linyeras*, *cirujas*, and *lunfardos*) were integrated into the scientific culture of the turn of the century as the grotesque contrast to those evolutionary patterns of human perfection. However, the popular culture of tango, theatre (*sainetes*) and the *feuilleton* of the first third of the twentieth century proposed an alternative image that, although it did not dissolve it, at least complicated the positivist antinomy queer/normative—healthy/unhealthy—able/disabled. Where positivism and naturalism sought social regeneration through logics of eugenic selection or seclusion (castration, imprisonment, or asylum life), the nexus tango-theater-*feuilleton* explored the manifestation of physical and cognitive impairment through a tragicomic and vulgar sentimentalism. This aesthetic formula became a pedagogical strategy that combined *kitsch* with anthropological renditions of the

underworlds of Buenos Aires to suggest that the moral and physical recovery of the tramp was necessary and desirable. Focusing on this popular character of the Río de la Plata and based on a critique informed by crip theory, this chapter examines how the aesthetic analysis of corporeal difference offers new methodologies to approach the notion of disability and the primary role it had in the context of literary modernization and the birth of modern ideas of citizenship, labor, and productive capacity. Texts considered are “Mujer que vivió como un atorrante.” (1915), “El atorrante de por acá” (1894, chronicle) by Rubén Darío, “El atorrante” (1910, tango) by Luis Galván, *El romance de un atorrante* (1921, novel) by José Antonio Saldías and *El linyera* (1929, theater) by Ivo Pelay, among others.

ANTICIPATED CONFERENCE, WORKSHOP ATTENDANCE, COURSES, AND /OR SEMINAR PRESENTATIONS:

COMPLETED SO FAR:

Conferences (These presentations were supported by the MSCA fellowship, and I was the **main speaker**. (Months 1 to 6)

1. 2024 Presentation at the Modern Language Association Convention 2024. Philadelphia, USA. “Eugenics Scripted: Reading Disability in the Ibero-Amerikanisches Institut Theatre Archive,” Carlos Gustavo Halaburda (U of Cologne). <https://www.k-saa.org/blog/romanticism-and-related-panels-at-mla-24>. 7.1.2024
2. 2024 Presentation at the University of Chicago. *Argentina’s Villainous Reproduction: Melodrama and the Making of Queerness and Disability in the Age of Eugenics*. USA. 10/1/2024. <https://voices.uchicago.edu/latinamericancarib/>
3. 2023 “French-Argentine Queer Transculturations: Machonas and Garçonnes in the Fin de Siècle. Global South Studies Center. University of Cologne, 23.11 <https://gssc.uni-koeln.de/personen/gastwissenschaftlerinnen/halaburda-carlos>
4. 2023 “A Cosmopolitan Uranism: Queer Networks of Scandal in the Global Nineteenth Century.” Centre for Latin American and Caribbean Studies. Centre for the Study of Sexuality and Culture. University of Manchester, United Kingdom. 15.11.2023 <https://events.manchester.ac.uk/event/event:k25x-lnxek6jr-adurag/carlos-halaburda-university-of-cologne-a-cosmopolitan-uranism-queer-networks-of-scandal-in-the-global-nineteenth-century>
5. 2023 “A Sentimental Disability: Melodrama, Gender Deviance, and Crip Bodies in Argentine Theatre.” Centre for Interdisciplinary Gender Studies. University of Leeds, UK, 15.11.2023. <https://gender-studies.leeds.ac.uk/carlos-halaburdas-presentation-queer-crip-theory-workshop/>

Attended Conferences and Workshops. University of Cologne (Month 1 to 6)

2024. Können Comics im Geschichtsunterricht ein Tool zur Vermittlung transatlantischer Schwarzer Geschichte sein? Organisation: J.-Prof. Dr. Jasmin Wrobel (RUB), Dr. Janek Scholz (UzK). Ort: Universität zu Köln, Neuer Senatssaal. 30.01.2024, 16-19 Uhr. <https://www.romanistik.de/aktuelles/7331>

2024 GSSC Seminar Series. 23 January 2024. Black Modernities, Aesthetics and Politics in Brazil. Center and Margins of National Thought (from the 19th to the 21st Century). Allan Santos da Rosa (University of Sao Paulo / Mecila). University of Cologne. <https://gssc.uni-koeln.de/en/veranstaltungen/gssc-seminar-reihe/gss-24-01-23-santos-darosa>. 24.1.2024

2024. Poetica. World Literature Festival. Opening Night. 19hs. University of Cologne. Philosophikum. 22.1.2023.

2023 Global South Studies Center. GSSC Seminar Series. 21 November 2023. On Idle Possibilities and Missed Chances: Refugee Rights in Egypt and the Current Response to the Sudanese Conflict (Elena Habersky, American University Cairo). 12:00-13:00.

2023 Indigenes Kino aus Brasilien. Die Filme von Alberto Guarani in der Filmpalette. 06.-08.11.2023

2023 Auerbach Workshop | 07.11.2023 | 10am Uhr Massimiliano Mollona “(Art, Anthropology, Bologna): ART/COMMONS. On communist art and the labour of the unartist.”

2023 Voces y Silencios. 6ta Jornada de Literatura Argentina. 23/10/2023. Universidad de Colonia. Alter Senatssaal.

2023 The Erich Auerbach Institute for Advanced Studies, Smells in German-Language Literature of the Long 19th Century. 19/10/2023. Weyertal 79.

Courses audited.

- Brazilian Visual Culture: Race, Gender, and Sexuality. Seminar. Prof. Dr. Peter Schulze. Sept-2023/Feb 2024. University of Cologne. Department of Romance Studies.

For other conference and outreach activities, see below, Communication Skills Plan

2. RESEARCH SKILLS AND TECHNIQUES:

- *Training in specific new areas, or technical expertise etc:*

My incorporation at Universität zu Köln entails a number of institutes of research excellence: I am a fellow in the Department of Romance Studies and the Portuguese Brazilian Institute, a visiting fellow in the Global South Studies Center, and an affiliated fellow at the Erich Auerbach Institute. My continuous contribution with these centers provides me with new and inspiring academic environments where I cultivate a revitalized research agenda. Prof. Dr. Schulze offers close mentorship and the encouragement to develop original, independent, and critical thinking. My partnership with Dr. Scholz from the PBI, with whom I created a research cluster on Latin American and Brazilian trans* cultural history, is becoming a long-standing collaboration. We are organizing a colloquium and a journal special issue.

The university provides extensive resources to develop professional skills, from research dissemination in academic settings to diversity and inclusion education initiatives outside academia. This postdoctoral residence in Germany is allowing me to acquire close links with researchers and centers specialized in Latin America, such as the Ibero-Amerikanisches Institut of Berlin, where I will be conducting research in May 2024. The IAI is the most extensive research library in Europe dedicated to Hispanic and Lusophone studies. Through the consultation of these archives, I will acquire new qualitative methods to approach literary sources thanks to the expertise of the librarians and the weekly research seminar at the IAI.

My residence in Cologne is facilitating continued participation in European academic gatherings where I engage in dialogues with international scholars, for example at The University of Manchester and at the University of Leeds. The current project aligns with and complement key areas of study that form an integral part of the institutes where I hold affiliation at UniKöln, such as clusters in race, gender, and sexuality studies. Immersive training across these domains will furnish me with a robust foundation to achieve the project's objectives. This contribution will entail keep organizing seminars, facilitating discussions, and fostering knowledge exchange opportunities.

Archives and libraries consulted during the training period (Month 1 to 6)

Archives consulted: Digital and Print

1. Ibero-Amerikanisches Institut - Stiftung Preußischer Kulturbesitz. <https://www.iai.spk-berlin.de/startseite.html>. Digital.
2. Hemeroteca Nacional de España. Hemeroteca Digital. <https://www.bne.es/es/catalogos/hemeroteca-digital>
3. Ahira. Archivo Histórico de Revistas Argentinas. Digital. <https://ahira.com.ar>
4. The University and City Library of Cologne. In Person.
5. The NS-Documentation Center of the City of Cologne Library—Queer Collection. In Person.
6. Manchester Central Library. In-Person and Digital. Archive of the People's History Museum of Manchester. Microfilm Collections on British Suffragism and World Feminist Networks. See details here: [http://gmlives.org.uk/results.html#imu\[rid=ecatalogue.262930\]](http://gmlives.org.uk/results.html#imu[rid=ecatalogue.262930])
7. Bibliothèque Nationale de France Digital Archives <https://www.bnf.fr/fr>

Archives to be consulted in person in months 9 and 10.

1. The Ibero-American Institute. Berlin. <https://www.iai.spk-berlin.de/startseite.html>
2. The National Library of France. <https://www.bnf.fr/fr>

3. RESEARCH MANAGEMENT:

1. Fellowships

Upon finalization of the MSCA program, I plan to apply for fellowships that will allow me to develop skills in numerous aspects of the profession: work programming, supervision, and resource management. Some of them are library research based. Some of them are long term residences, some major grants. This is a long-term objective as I am currently already in a major grant (MSCA.) I researched the following fellowships schemes, and I may consider any of them.

1. Senior Fellowship. Mecila (Maria Sibylla Merian International Centre for Advanced Studies in the Humanities and Social Sciences Conviviality-Inequality in Latin America). São Paulo. German Federal Ministry of Education and Research (BMBF). <https://mecila.net/en/>
2. Social Sciences and Humanities Research Council of Canada. SSHRC's Insight Research program. https://www.sshrc-crsh.gc.ca/funding-financement/umbrella_programs-programme_cadre/insight-savoir-eng.aspx
3. Friends of the Princeton University Library. <https://library.princeton.edu/special-collections/friends-princeton-university-library-research-grants>
4. Alexander von Humboldt Foundation: Humboldt Research Fellowships for Postdoctoral Researchers. <https://www2.daad.de/deutschland/stipendium/datenbank/en/21148-scholarship-database/?status=2&origin=32&subjectGrps=&daad=&intention=&q=&page=2&detail=10000110>
5. Fritz Thyssen Foundation: Postdoc Stipends. <https://www2.daad.de/deutschland/stipendium/datenbank/en/21148-scholarship-database/?status=2&origin=32&subjectGrps=&daad=&intention=&q=&page=3&detail=10000140>
6. Gerda Henkel Foundation: Research Scholarships. <https://www2.daad.de/deutschland/stipendium/datenbank/en/21148-scholarship-database/?status=2&origin=32&subjectGrps=&daad=&intention=&q=&page=3&detail=10000130>
7. German Research Foundation (DFG): Research Grant. <https://www2.daad.de/deutschland/stipendium/datenbank/en/21148-scholarship-database/?status=2&origin=32&subjectGrps=&daad=&intention=&q=&page=3&detail=10000161>
8. Research Stays for University Academics and Scientists • DAAD. <https://www2.daad.de/deutschland/stipendium/datenbank/en/21148-scholarship-database/?status=2&origin=32&subjectGrps=&daad=&intention=&q=&page=1&detail=50015456>

9. The Ibero-American Institute (IAI) Library Grant. <https://www.iai.spk-berlin.de/en/grants.html>

2. Open Science Training

I attended one event in Open Science Training in the Humanities. I will attend another one in 2024.

1. Personal Communication with i. A. Jasmin Schenk (M.A., M. LIS). 27/10/2023
Geschäftsführung Cologne Competence Center for Research Data Management - C³RDM
<https://fdm.uni-koeln.de/> (**Achieved**)
2. NCP ERC Webinar on Open Science in ERC projects (19.03.2024, 13:00-14:30).

3. COMMUNICATION SKILLS:

The Marie Skłodowska Curie Postdoctoral Fellowship allows me the opportunity for refining my presentation skills, research, and communication abilities. Participating in international conferences, workshops, and seminars aligns with my career development plan and will significantly contribute to the advancement of my research work and communication proficiency. The findings of my research project will be disseminated through various initiatives aimed at both academic audiences and the general public, following the dissemination guidelines of the University of Cologne and the MSCA.

As I can be seen in the number of initiatives in which I was the main presenter or attendee, my activity at the University of Cologne has been considerably active. The plan is to continue emanating and mobilizing research results inside and outside the university. I plan to keep the focus on the publication and communication of research conclusions to a broad audience. For example, I was invited to give a night lecture in the Círculo Machado of Cologne, the main Spanish cultural centre of the city. I will give a lecture on queer cultures of Buenos Aires' 1920s on March 15th. <https://spanischer-verein.com>.

The transmission and dissemination process will incorporate actions in the host institutions and exterior ones through conferences, workshop seminars, public lectures, social engagement activities, participation in scientific symposia, and academic publications.

So far, the following conferences and workshops are confirmed for 2024:

- LASA Congress Bogotá, June 2024. <https://lasaweb.org/en/>
- The Queer Life of 1920s Buenos Aires: Tango, Casinos, and Theatres in the Urban Novel. Círculo Machado, Cologne. <https://spanischer-verein.com>

Future conferences:

Latin American Studies Association Congress (2025)

Society for Latin American Studies (SLAS) Annual Conference 2025 (UK)

Other initiatives are being considered at the moment for the years 2024 and 2025.

5. OTHER PROFESSIONAL TRAINING (COURSE WORK, TEACHING ACTIVITY):

1. Teaching:

During the Winter Semester 2023-2024, I taught an advanced seminar. My module was called **LGBTQ Latin America**. I taught this advanced seminar at the Department of Romance Studies of the University of Cologne. It was conducted in 15 sessions. See the syllabus here:

https://www.carloshalaburda.com/_files/ugd/948761_c506329263d346658a59a7e39e299c57.pdf

The syllabus will be uploaded along with other data (critical bibliography of my project) to the trusted depository Xenodo. <https://zenodo.org>.

2. Supervision and mentoring of advanced students:

These types of activities will be evaluated at the appropriate moment, whenever the chance presents itself.

6. ANTICIPATED NETWORKING OPPORTUNITIES

Maximizing networking opportunities will be a vital element of the project to ensure academic and professional growth. One crucial aspect is building strong relationships with my advisor and faculty members in the Romance Studies department through regular discussions, seeking feedback on research ideas, and participating in departmental events. I also plan to explore partnerships with new research centers focusing on gender and sexuality studies and Latin American Studies.

I organized the following events at The University of Cologne (Month 1 to 6)

2024 *A Questao Do Queer e Do Trans Na Literatura Contemporanea. Apresentacao, Conversa com Cris Judar e Carlos Halaburda*. January 18th, 2024. 2pm. Philosophikum S84. University of Cologne.

2023 *The Woman who Loved Horses: Gambling and Sapphic Pleasures in the Uruguayan Novecientos*. 28/11/2023. Online. 4pm Cologne. Guest Lecture with Jesse Rothbard, PhD Candidate Northwestern University USA.

2023 *Un tornado alrededor. (A Tornado Surrounding Us)*. Conversation with Dr. Facundo Abal about his Argentine coming-of-age queer novel. 27/10/2023. Online.

I also began implementing my networking plan by serving as the Chair of the Nineteenth Century Section of the Latin American Studies Association. See details here: <https://lasaweb.org/en/sections/nineteenth-century/>. I oversaw the following activities during the first year as the Chair of the Section (Sept 2023-Present):

- 1. Organization of Sponsored Panels.** LASA2024 Hybrid Congress: Reacción y resistencia: Imaginar futuros posibles en las Américas taking place June 12–15, 2024, virtually and on-site in Bogota, Colombia at the Pontificia Universidad Javeriana. **The Panels are entitled:**
 1. "LGBTQ Fin de Siècle in Latin America"

2. "Magic, Science, Spectacle: Exhibition and Knowledge in Nineteenth-Century Popular Venues"

2. Organization of LASA Nineteenth Century Panel

"Moda, alimentación, imagen: estéticas higienistas del cuerpo finisecular" Part 1 and 2

3. Organization of LASA Nineteenth Century and Sexualities Panel

"Los desafíos del archivo efímero en América Latina"

4. Organization of LASA 2024 Nineteenth Century Section Pre-Conference

I engaged more than 25 (twenty-five) scholars from Europe and the Americas to participate in these initiatives in Colombia this coming June 2024.

5. Coordination of the section's awards to best book, article and dissertation of the year 2023.

See <https://lasaweb.org/en/sections/nineteenth-century/>

The Programs of the Congress will available here: <https://lasaweb.org/en/lasa2024/program>

Networking Opportunities at The University of Cologne:

As for networking opportunities at The University of Cologne, due to the connections I established with the Welcome Center (<https://portal.uni-koeln.de/international/internationale-forschende>), I was invited to participate in two initiatives.

- 1) Lectureship of Gender and/or LGBTQ studies and cultural production for a course in the summer semester in the Cologne Global Study Program. In review.
<https://portal.uni-koeln.de/en/international/studium-in-koeln/cologne-global-study-program-cgsp>
- 2) Lecture at the Cologne International Forum. Date to be announced.
<https://cif.uni-koeln.de/events>

Other research institutes to be contacted in the future to increase visibility of my project and networking opportunities:

Department of Romance Studies. Humboldt University
<https://www.romanistik.hu-berlin.de/de>

University of Amsterdam Research Centre for Gender and Sexuality
<https://arcs.uva.nl/>

Institut Für Romanische Philologie. Berlin.
<https://www.geisteswissenschaften.fu-berlin.de/we05/index.html>

7. OTHER ACTIVITIES (COMMUNITY, ETC) WITH PROFESSIONAL RELEVANCE:

Currently, there are no other defined professional activities or practices.